

Supplementary Material

Supplementary material includes chemical compositions of the starting materials (Table S1) and phases coexistence with bridgmanite for B, D, F, and H compositions (Table S2), and Lattice parameters of phases in the recovered samples (Table S3).

Table S1. Chemical compositions of the starting material.

Letter	Start Comp	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Total	Mg	Al	Si	Sum
Comp in En–Brm									
A	En ₉₀ Brm ₁₀ (n = 15)	39.49 (18)	5.11 (5)	55.08 (37)	99.68 (40)	0.992 (6)	0.102 (1)	0.928 (3)	2.021 (3)
B	En ₅₂ Brm ₄₈ (n = 8)	39.09 (48)	26.48 (38)	33.37 (82)	98.89 (119)	1.018 (17)	0.545 (2)	0.582 (7)	2.145 (8)
Comp. in En–Sp									
C	En ₉₅ Sp ₅ (n = 25)	38.42 (32)	5.05 (9)	56.16 (36)	99.62 (54)	0.962 (6)	0.100 (2)	0.944 (3)	2.006 (3)
D	En ₅₀ Sp ₅₀ (n = 5)	32.91 (62)	39.19 (56)	27.84 (56)	99.94 (80)	0.846 (13)	0.796 (10)	0.480 (9)	2.112 (7)
Comp. in En–Cor									
E	En ₉₅ Cor ₅ (n = 15)	38.42 (29)	5.10 (5)	57.47 (48)	100.99 (52)	0.948 (9)	0.100 (2)	0.951 (7)	1.999 (7)
F	En ₅₀ Cor ₅₀ (n = 7)	20.25 (17)	49.72 (41)	30.51 (19)	100.48 (35)	0.506 (4)	0.982 (6)	0.511 (4)	1.998 (2)
Comp. in En–Ky									
G	En ₉₅ Ky ₅ (n = 30)	35.88 (30)	5.09 (12)	57.98 (67)	98.95 (75)	0.899 (9)	0.101 (2)	0.975 (5)	1.975 (5)
H	En ₅₀ Ky ₅₀ (n = 8)	15.21 (61)	37.96 (55)	47.26 (71)	100.43 (95)	0.369 (14)	0.728 (7)	0.769 (11)	1.867 (8)

Oxide analyses are reported in wt.%, and the number of cation is shown based on the oxygen number is normalized to 3. Number in parentheses represents standard deviation for the last digit (s). n: the number of analysis points. (Note: the oxide mixture were compressed into a very dense pellet by a jack for composition measurement).

Table S2. Chemical compositions of phases coexistence with bridgmanite for B, D, F, and H compositions.

Let	Phases	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Total	O	Mg	Al	Si	Sum	mol.%	mol.%
	CF phase										Mg ₂ SiO ₄	MgAl ₂ O ₄
B	n = 20	37.54 (40)	46.85 (50)	14.06 (34)	98.54 (54)	4	1.341 (12)	1.324 (13)	0.337 (8)	3.001 (5)	34 (2)	66 (2)
B*	n = 23	37.31 (48)	46.01 (48)	14.76 (46)	98.08 (44)	4	1.336 (17)	1.303 (15)	0.355 (10)	2.994 (7)	35 (1)	65 (1)
D	n = 22	34.94 (35)	52.41 (51)	11.93 (40)	99.29 (51)	4	1.236 (12)	1.466 (12)	0.283 (9)	2.984 (6)	30 (2)	70 (2)
D*	n = 24	35.11 (34)	51.69 (60)	12.25 (30)	99.05 (73)	4	1.245 (11)	1.449 (11)	0.294 (6)	2.984 (4)	29 (1)	71 (1)
	Cor										Al ₂ O ₃	MgSiO ₃
D	n = 8	7.64 (50)	80.97 (70)	11.02 (74)	99.63 (71)	3	0.193 (12)	1.622 (19)	0.187 (12)	2.002 (5)	81 (1)	19 (1)
D*	n = 13	7.54 (26)	80.86 (67)	11.41 (31)	99.63 (71)	3	0.190 (7)	1.615 (9)	0.193 (5)	1.999 (3)	81 (1)	19 (1)
F	n = 10	8.37 (50)	78.22 (87)	12.04 (37)	98.64 (69)	3	0.214 (13)	1.582 (13)	0.207 (6)	2.003 (4)	79 (1)	21 (1)
H	n = 11	7.79 (30)	80.07 (57)	11.49 (48)	99.35 (56)	3	0.198 (7)	1.607 (13)	0.196 (8)	2.001 (2)	80 (1)	20 (1)
	Other phases										Al ₂ O ₃	
B	Per (n = 5)	99.22 (41)	0.68 (6)	–	99.90 (46)	1	0.992 (1)	0.005 (0)	–	0.997 (1)	0.3 (0)	
B*	Per (n = 4)	98.44 (55)	0.71 (7)	–	99.17 (59)	1	0.991 (1)	0.006 (0)	–	0.997 (1)	0.3 (0)	
H	Sti (n = 9)	0.34 (21)	3.79 (80)	94.40 (53)	98.52 (64)	2	0.005 (3)	0.046 (10)	0.963 (8)	1.014 (3)	2.0 (1)	

Oxide analyses are reported in wt.%. n: number of analysis points. Number in parentheses represents standard deviation for the last digit (s). Abbreviations: CF phase: calcium ferrite-type structure of MgAl₂O₄; Per, periclase; Sti, stishovite.

Table S3. Lattice parameters of phases in the recovered samples.

Run No.	Comp	Phases	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	Molar V (cm ³ /mol)
IRIS423	A	Brg	4.780 (2)	4.934 (3)	6.930 (4)	163.31 (34)	24.59 (3)
	E	Brg	4.776 (3)	4.924 (3)	6.922 (5)	162.78 (36)	24.51 (5)
IRIS427	B	Brg	4.780 (2)	4.936 (7)	6.920 (6)	163.27 (34)	24.58 (5)
	F	Brg	4.780 (3)	4.938 (6)	6.927 (8)	163.50 (49)	24.62 (5)
		Cor	4.769 (4)	–	13.030 (5)	256.64 (42)	25.74 (6)
IRIS446	D	Brg	4.795 (9)	4.923 (8)	6.928 (9)	163.54 (83)	24.62 (5)
		CF	9.963 (15)	8.629 (18)	2.799 (6)	240.66 (133)	36.22 (4)
		Cor	4.764 (1)	–	13.019 (2)	255.89 (20)	25.67 (6)
	H	Brg	4.774 (4)	4.940 (5)	6.932 (2)	163.53 (9)	24.62 (5)
		Cor	4.771 (3)	–	13.012 (1)	256.57 (34)	25.74 (5)
		Sti	4.189 (2)	–	2.663 (3)	46.73 (24)	14.01 (1)
IRIS450	C	Brg	4.778 (2)	4.929 (4)	6.920 (4)	162.98 (31)	24.54 (4)
	G	Brg	4.775 (4)	4.925 (4)	6.919 (5)	162.71 (35)	24.50 (5)

–: the same value of a-axis

Number in parentheses represents standard deviation for the last digit (s).